

Women's Land Use Performance and Production Constrains: Gender Disparity in Southwest Ethiopia's Agricultural Investment

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Abstract

Gender disparity in agricultural investment in Ethiopia remain a significant challenge, particularly in the Southwest, where women face systemic constraints to land, resource allocation and productivity. Although women comprise large portion of the agricultural labour force, their agricultural performance is impeded by a combination of limits on land ownership, the ability to access finance and agricultural inputs. This study investigated the land use performance and production constraints faced by women agricultural investors in Southwest Ethiopia. It found considerable gender disparities, with male investors not only securing more land (mean land area = 293 hectares, mean land area for women = 134 hectares) but also significantly higher mean access to capital (22.5 million Birr versus 15.8 million Birr for women). Women faced near total exclusion from credit (0% access), and tax privileges (0% access). Moreover, while joint ownership was observed to be a positive model for agricultural output, women were still limited in productivity. The finding also revealed that women had considerably less area cultivated with rain fed crops, and that smallholder efficiency existed where resources were evident. Moreover, structural barriers which included the complete lack of policy support for women in agriculture, the susceptibility to climate risks or hazards (40% of women compared to 8.9. %) and institutional factors bias women in agricultural Investment. This study recommends gender audits of agricultural programs, cooperative mechanism leasing to increase gender equity, and providing better extension services to narrow the productivity gap. Addressing constraints facing women mean capitalizing on the full potential women in contributing to agricultural production and advance domestic economic growth and gender equity constraints are addressed, Ethiopia can

Keywords: Gender Disparity, Women, Agricultural Investment, Land use Performance, Ethiopia

1. Introduction

1. Background of the Study

Agriculture is foundational to food security and economic development in the world. It is particularly important in developing countries where agriculture has a large share of the labour force. Women make up about 43% of the agricultural labour force in developing countries (FAO, 2021), but they continue to be severely constrained by systemic barriers that limit their productivity, land ownership claims, and decision-making power. Barriers remain despite Ethiopia's progressive agricultural policies, including the Agriculture Development Led Industrialization (ADLI) strategy launched in 1993 and Growth and Transformation Plans (GTP) White Papers aimed at transforming the sector from subsistence to commercial agriculture.

Recently, researches increasingly emphasized on the behavioral determinants of women's economic decision-making in recent years. Nirmala and Arulkumar (2024) stated that psychological and sociological factors as the behavior determinants of women investors in commodity markets, risk aversion attitude, dependence on past information, and rational choice

behavior. Although their paper has good insights into investor behavior, it is focused on financial markets and not on how this behavior may contribute to land use decision-making and investment in farming by women. Buabeng et al. (2024) argued that customary inheritance law severely restricting access to cultivable land by women. Even when women participate in farming, their access to land is often symbolic, marital status-based, or in male dominance. This reality restricts their long-term investment autonomy and decision-making independence. Russo et al. (2024), in European agricultural investment patterns systematic review, pointed out that there are significant effects of endogenous farm factors and exogenous policy factors on land investment decisions, yet women's voices could hardly be heard in the dominant discourse. Chu et al. (2023) confirmed that women owned significantly fewer lands compared to men and even earned less from agricultural investment. Gender differences in land ownership are translated into differences in agricultural output performance instantly.

Across the African continent, there are some general trends. Women have become largely involved in low-capital, labor-intensive food crop production, whereas men dominate high-value crop chains and large-scale farming enterprises. Studies in Ghana, Nigeria, Cameroon, and other countries have also identified similar constraints, such as poor access to inputs, markets, and productive assets. Such studies also highlight that while women's labor is critical in agricultural production, their decision-making authority and investment autonomy remain restricted. Also, most of the current research adopts the problem-solving strategy—single-case descriptions of the constraints but minimal or no experimentation with solutions or evaluation of the impact of targeted policies for women empowerment. For example, Bhati et al. (2022) compared trained and untrained women farmers' utilization of resources without examining the structural barriers to training programs being linked to improved outcomes. Soumya (2022) also pointed to the lack of gender-disaggregated data as one of the primary methodological concerns that inhibit evidence-based policy-making. A few studies also point towards the need for intersectional analysis that considers the way in which caste, class, and education interact with gender in determining agricultural outcomes (Satpathy & Astariyani, 2023; Renu, 2023). In Ethiopia, agriculture and rural development policy, which began with the Agricultural Development Led Industrialization (ADLI) strategy in 1993, put smallholder agriculture at the center of economic growth. As strategic plans of ADLI policy documents such SDPRP (2002/03-2004/05), PASDEP (2005/06-2009/10), and GTP (2010/11-2014/15) priority smallholder agriculture. In addition, the government policy implementation of the Rural Development Policy and Strategy (RDPS) and the Food Security Strategy (FSS), aimed to promote smallholder productivity through improved inputs, extension services, irrigation and improved rural infrastructure. Most importantly, PASDEP (2006) and GTP (2010) began to promote the idea of large-scale commercial farming which involved private sector investment and therefore required transformation of the agricultural sector as a whole and therefore assumes a degree of or promotes industrialization in the agricultural sector. As a centerpiece to the plan for achieving food security (which is certainly an issue in Ethiopia given the history) and achieving middle-income status by 2025, the plan argues for an increase in cultivated land from 986,492 hectares in 2020 to 4.2 million hectares by 2030.

Despite legislation and proclamations exist in Ethiopia to secure women's equal access to and control over land, the patriarchal nature of customary inheritance practices and the persistence of deeply held cultural norms still restrict women's access to and control over land. Patriarchal inheritance systems and cultural values, despite constitutional guarantees and liberal land proclamations, remain bound to confine women's rights over land. Empirical findings have indicated that female-headed households own smaller farms, fewer livestock, and less access to credit and extension services than male-headed households (Abdisa et al., 2024; Gebrehiwot & Ndinda, 2024). The variations yield lower productive potential and limited scope for investment in agriculture.

A meta-analysis conducted by Asefa & Muluken (2024) revealed that smallholder farms (≤ 0.5 hectares), typically headed by women, were 21% more productive than large-scale farms. Still, such gains in efficiency are rarely translated to access to capital or the ability to expand land. Women-owned maize farms also enjoyed superior technical efficiency scores with more limited access to inputs, as observed by (Alemu et al., 2024). These findings show that women can produce high levels when they have an equivalent amount of resources, but structural problems tend to prevent them from expanding. In Southern Ethiopia, Gebrehiwot and Ndinda (2024) demonstrated that women's labor burdens, especially domestic care work, significantly limit women's time for farm work. In Gamo Zone, Jemaneh & Shibeshi (2023) demonstrated that empowering women in agriculture led to significant gains in dietary diversity and food security. Yet, their empowerment is tenuous and context-dependent, bounded by broader sociocultural and institutional determinants.

Although there are growing recognition of gender disparity in Agriculture, empirical Literature shown to have significant limitation. Particularly, women's land use performance and production constraints remain in Southwest Ethiopia is uninvestigated. In spite of evidence of productivity differentials between male- and female-headed farms in the literature (Abdisa et al., 2024), the literature lacks detailed analysis of how psychological traits like risk aversion interact with structural barriers in commercial farming arrangements (Nirmala & Arulkumar, 2024; Chu et al., 2023). Region-specific research is particularly scarce in Southwest Ethiopia, where the unique gendered politics of land commercialization and climate exposure are less well-researched than in other places (Gebrehiwot & Ndinda, 2024; Jemaneh & Shibeshi, 2023). Also, while women's workloads are thoroughly researched (Asefa & Muluken, 2024), there is fewer examinations of how these constraints do (or don't) interact with access to mechanization, irrigation, and climate-resilient agriculture - despite evidence that these technologies could close gender gaps if well-designed (Belay et al., 2022). Policy application is also beset by evaluation gaps, insofar as research has not adequately investigated if land certification programs actually translate into more investment flexibility or productivity for women (Holden & Tilahun, 2020; Tsige et al., 2020). Most egregious is that research has overwhelmingly focused on smallholder subsistence farming and overlooked medium- and large-scale women investors, who are systemically denied access to credit and machinery availability (Alemu et al., 2024). Such gaps with behavioral-economic studies, regionally targeted research, technology adoption studies, and policy analysis with rigorous designs could constitute an important contribution to gender equity in Ethiopian agriculture.

The study is intended to assess the land use performance of women investors in agricultural investment and their productivity in the Southwest Regional State of Ethiopia. This research fills the gaps by looking at women as agricultural investors. In so doing, it offers evidence on how Southwest Ethiopia can harness the full potential of its agriculture through mechanisms of in-depth and evidence-based gender policy. The study contributes twofold to existing empirical literature. First, it offers gender-disaggregated examinations of land use performance within Ethiopia's Southwest Regional State. It provides region-specific information on women's engagement with land markets and overcoming structural barriers. Secondly, apart from mere labeling of bottlenecks, the study addresses specific, realistic interventions such as gender-sensitive land lease, cooperative membership, and credit arrangements that can allow women to engage in entrepreneurship.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Main Approaches to Gender Inclusion in Development

The theoretical development of women's agricultural empowerment involved over time. The **Women in Development (WID)** approach appeared in the 1970s emphasized on the contribution of women to agricultural production systems. Tinker (1976) and Buvinić (1976) extended of the Boserup's(1970) ideas to adress developing WID projects to involve women as they integrated them into development interventions through improved agricultural technologies and access to delivery (Rogers 1980). As Staudt (1985) illustrated in her case studies of Kenya, these early WID approaches were often productive for women but failed to challenge important aspects of the patriarchal structure of women's relations to land and decision-making.

By the 1980s the **Gender and development (GAD)** paradigm emerged to help consider these limitations in WID, with Moser (1989) and Kabeer (1994) underlining the relevance of examining power relations and institutional constraints. This was at the same time as key revelations were being made regarding the effects of structural adjustment policies in WID frameworks and how they produced adverse effects for women farmers with environmental degradation combined with diminished agricultural extension services (Gladwin 1991), and increasing burdens of reproductive labour (Elson 1991). GAD set the stage for feminist political ecology (FPE) in the 1990s by introducing intersectional analyses of gendered access to natural resources and the intersectional effects of environmental change (Rocheleau et al. 1996; Agarwal 1992). Key uses of FPE in studies took place in relation to community forestry programs (Agarwal 2010) and water management systems (Zwarteveen 1997), which illustrated ways in which environmental processes often recreated existing, if not increased gender inequalities, however, did little to dismantle gender inequalities.

2.2. Theoretical Foundations

Feminist economics emerged as a response to the failure of neoclassical theory that treats households and markets as if they were gender-neutral spaces (Elson, 1995; Ferber & Nelson, 2003). It brings to the forefront how structural inequality and social norms regularly depreciate women's labor, particularly unpaid care and subsistence farming. Feminist economists argue in agriculture that differences in gender productivity are a measure of women's inefficiency but actually structural barriers to women's access to land, credit, and technology (Agarwal, 1994; Doss et al., 2018).

In the Ethiopian context, this model focuses on how women's contributions in agriculture remain invisible in planning and policy (Druzca, 2019). Although they constitute nearly half of all those in agriculture, women are excluded from high-value crops and commercial investment by gender norms deeply rooted in society. Feminist economics therefore introduces the elementary framework for analysis that inequalities in investment do not occur randomly but are determined by structural power relations.

Bargaining and Intra-Household Models

The bargaining model dispenses with the neoclassical unitary household assumption (Sen, 1990; Agarwal, 1997). Household members are rather viewed as arenas of negotiation in which members possess unequal bargaining power due to their fallback positions and resource endowments. Women's limited rights of ownership of land and capital erode their bargaining position, giving them restricted voice in household investment choices, cropping patterns, and the use of income. In Ethiopia, research reveals that even in joint ownership arrangements, decision-making by women is only relinquished since men hold the title to land and are more easily accessible for capital (Bayu et al., 2021). Joint holdings, then, even though of a higher

order, are not necessarily linked to equal levels of empowerment. Bargaining theory, thus, provides an explanation for intra-household dynamics for why inequality persists in the presence of seeming progress.

Institutional Economics

Institutional Economics, pioneered by the Douglas North 1980s, about the "rules of the game", i.e. the formal and informal institutions governing access to resources to determine the outcomes of economic activities. Institutions generate a system of inclusion and exclusion in outcomes from economic activities taking place from the allocation of resources. For example, in the agriculture sector, the differential effects of resource investments and decision-making outcomes often derives from institutional impediments or biases under each rule, including structural issues with land titles and inherited ownership predominantly by males or men (Meinzen-Dick et al., 2019). Married couples may have inherited or acquired land, in the context, have been subjected to laws that stipulated and provided: outcomes for nominally gender sensitive agricultural sector policies without addressing the serious issues of systemic discrimination, a lack of institutional enforcement and remaining structural barriers (Tsigie et al., 2020). Examples of these conventions are the formal rights of the certificate holders listing women as claiming or secondary or marginal title holders who possessed fewer rights that are limited --wherein women lacked considerable autonomy and resources for bargaining position in intra-household negotiations (Holden & Tefera, 2008). Simply stated, institutional economics considers inequality as an inherent structural barrier, and rejects any preconceived notions of individual or sustainable incapacity of the community or the individual being dependent on external support as reasons to exclude women from property rights, land tenure schemes and negotiations.

Capability Approach

The capability approach, launched by Sen (1999) and built on by Nussbaum (2000), shifts focus from resources to what people can be and do—their capabilities. The approach recognizes that resources may not mean empowerment because conversion factors (cultural, institutional, technological) determine whether people are or are not able to convert assets into functioning's. For women farmers, land or credit access does not automatically equate to empowerment if cultural norms prevent them from exercising autonomy in decision-making, or extension services fail to provide commensurate training (Kabeer, 1999). This is true in Ethiopia; women landowners can be underpinned by patriarchal norms excluding them from autonomy in the use or sale of land. The capability approach is therefore relevant to identifying the multidimensional constrains on women's economic agency.

These systematic theoretical literature shows ongoing tensions between three broad models of women's agricultural empowerment: (1) liberal economic models that emphasize closing the measurable productivity gap in outputs through new technologies and market access (FAO, 2011), (2) critical feminist and decolonial models that see empowerment in terms of land restitution and resource sovereignty and dismantling enduring colonial relations of dispossession, and (3) an intersectional model that pays attention to micro-level policies such as the SDGs, gender norms calibrated for each locality, and inequitable structures that sustain the subordination of women (Esluk, 2018; Winder, 2023).

These tensions indicate an ideological divide between interventions focused on symptoms (increase women's crop yield) and interventions that consider and attempt to address root causes (what systems of power remain in patriarchy and colonialism). As the metaphor of the "gender tree" emphasized confirmatively, transformative change requires combining asset land redistribution (e.g., land titles, credit) with systemic challenges to existing gender norms and colonial hierarchies; while the latter were seldom integrated into the former, the systematic

rejection of integration was more common. Integration of asset redistribution (e.g., women's land titles, women's access to credit) with systemic challenges have not been built into mainstream policy. The West and Global North are caught up in technocratic solutions to so-called "gender inequalities," which permit procedural justice to masquerade as substantive justice (Eslik; 2018; Winder, 2023).

Though each lens captures distinct perspective, together they form a comprehensive framework for understanding gender inequality. Structural inequality is explained by feminist economics, bargaining models illuminate intra-household power dynamics, institutional economics identifies governance bottlenecks in the system, and capability approach singles out agency and empowerment. Together, they advance the analysis beyond "what is happening" to "why are inequalities stuck" and create the platform for deciding "how to fix them" via strategic reforms.

2.3. Review of Empirical Insights

Land holding and gender imbalance in agricultural investment is a serious concern in developing and developed countries. Women are constrained by the unavailability of inputs, land, financial facilities, and decision-making for their participation in making their optimum contribution to rural development and agriculture production. This review critically evaluates recent empirical studies that look into gender relations in agriculture with specific reference to land use, investment decision, productivity, and institutional barriers. The goal is to determine patterns, regional specificities, and areas of knowledge gaps that can guide the subsequent of studies as well as policy intervention.

2.3.1 Global Evidence on Gender and Agricultural Investment

Nirmala and Arulkumar (2024) examined the women's investment decisions by exploring commodity market decisions from behavioral and psychological standpoints. Based on what their findings identify, risk aversion and preference to over-rely on historical information are some of the inclinations common among such women, characterizing them with high affinity to belief systems and rational choice. Chu et al. (2023) utilized publicly available administrative data to study the gender gap in land ownership in Taiwan, according to their results, men owned significantly more land and received larger yearly returns. Within the quasi-experimental research design, the study separated observational biases from actual gaps and provided empirical evidence of diligently derived gender gaps in land availability and investment performance. Bhati et al. (2022) researched the resource use efficiency of trained and untrained farm women in Gujarat, India. They found that knowledge certainly increased following training but did not lead to the effective employment of farm inputs, rather indicating deeper structural constraints such as poor market access and finance connections. This finding identifies a critical knowledge gap in the failure to document constraints beyond a knowledge deficit constraining the productivity of women in agriculture. Nguyen and Le (2022) examined the bargaining capacity of rural Vietnamese women with respect to landholding. According to cross-sectional household surveys, they found that women invest more in human capital in the form of education and health as land tenure becomes more secure.

In Africa, cultural and institutional barriers exaggerated gender disparity in agricultural investment. Buabeng et al. (2024) emphasized how gender inequality in land tenure for Ghanaian cocoa farmers. The study confirmed that women barely own land in their own names and inherit land via their marriage or family status. This limited tenorial control limited their autonomy in production decision-making. Likewise, using Tobit regression model, Adekunle et al. (2024) analyzed women's bargaining power over land in farm households in rural Nigeria. They established that bargaining power generally was not good for women, with marital status being the key determinant. The authors demonstrate with their study how the kinship and social organization limit women from having a say over agricultural investment decisions.

Nigerian agricultural survey of 2023 reports women who owned land accounted for 19.8% and literacy constraint, restriction on credit, and government support were the main hindrances to women's participation in farm production. Using Purposive sampling and random sampling, it identified structural imbalances that reduce the participation of women in investing in agriculture. Nigeria gender innovation (2023) also estimated Nigeria's productivity gap between male and female farmers. Female farmers produced 30% lower per hectare due to their restricted access to inputs, poor extension service coverage, and exclusion from high-value crop value chains. This paper presents one of the few empirical estimates of systemic gender-based productivity constraints. Chobe (2023) explored the role of land grabs in Cameroon and how they impacted women disproportionately. It was found that even though women contribute significantly to subsistence agriculture, they had no voice over land either legally or traditionally. This led to low food security and livelihood risk for female-headed families. Overall, these studies demonstrate that while women contribute significantly to agricultural production in Africa, discriminatory land tenure systems and the neglect of women's economic opportunities by formal institutions contribute to the persistence of inefficiencies and poverty. In Ethiopia, empirical studies provided sound insights on Land Use and Agricultural Efficiency. Asefa and Muluken (2024) meta-analysis showed that smaller farms (≤ 0.5 hectares) were 21% more efficient than larger farms and that the efficiency heterogeneity was linked to resource endowment and quality of labor 416. I find that observation interesting when we consider the conventional thinking on economies of scale in smallholder agriculture. Women typically have smaller farms than men, and the added level of efficiency may imply that women farmer would be achieving more efficiency potentially per unit area when provided enough resources. Despite this, there is a wealth of research that shows significant productivity disadvantages for female-headed households. Abdisa et al. (2024) reported that female-headed households were altogether, 3.7% less productive, and were behind their male counterparts by 11.2% and 5% by using their output in birr and quintals per hectare respectively 10. Gebre et al. (2021) found much larger differences in maize productivity and claimed male-headed households had 44.3% higher productivity, but they also noted equal allocation of resources would increase female productivity by 42.3% [Citation:13]. Their findings indicate that most of the gender productivity gap is attributable to non-uniform access to inputs and not the capacity of the farmers.

Alemu et al. (2022) identified that women-managed households attained higher technical efficiency (TE) and economic efficiency (EE) scores in maize production than men-managed households - albeit with less access to inputs. Alemu et al. (2024) in their study of gender and extension had found that if the relationship with respondents can be improved with gender-sensitive inputs and technology, they could potentially produce an additional 14.4 % in productivity gains 8. Across these studies on efficiency suggest that women farmers are usually able to get the maximum output from the limited range of resources available to them, if these women were supported with less resource constraints - the potential may be considerable.

An increasing number of empirical studies recognizes a variety of interrelated factors contributing to gender inequalities in agricultural productivity. Access to land is viewed as a fundamental constraint, where Women's needs are not always considered in land policies (Tsige et al. ,2020. Addis et al. (2020) employed Oaxaca decomposition to estimate the productivity gap between female- and male-headed households. In the article, they recorded a 3.7% overall productivity gap expanding to 11.2% value and 5% area. The gaps resulted from differential access to resources, particularly land and inputs. In a study of land registry data, Holden & Tilahun (2022) found that shares of females in landholding were as high as 48.8% by 2016, but did not distinguish land holdings by plot size or quality. Access to complementary resources presents further constraints. Gebre et al. (2021) analyzed market participation dynamics in Southern Ethiopia. With ordered probit and Blinder-Oaxaca decomposition

models, they saw that female and both-spouse-headed households were less likely to be net sellers. This restricted their access to commercial income and its re-investment into agriculture. Overall, Global, African, and Ethiopian empirical evidence all concur that women are underutilized yet vital actors in agricultural productivity and investment. While many studies capture gender differentials in land ownership, the utilization of inputs, and market participation, fewer provide tough analyses of determinants and solutions to the differentials. This is particularly serious in region like Southwest Ethiopia, where there is intensified commercial investment. Second, few region-specific studies have been carried out in Ethiopia. It is common for studies to extrapolate findings across the country without factoring in cultural and institutional specificities in places like the Southwest where customary land inheritance might be deeply ingrained. Third, there are limited studies on the effect of technology adoption or climate adaptation on women's productivity. In spite of its seeming importance, empirical evidence remains limited regarding the influence of mechanization and irrigation on gendered agricultural outcomes. Bringing these gaps in knowledge into closure is central to building inclusive agricultural policies that enhance women's agency, productivity, and economic empowerment in commercial and subsistence farming systems.

2.4. Conceptual Framework

Based on the theoretical discussion and a selection of empirical literature, the following section proposes a change framework that considers both structural determinants and pragmatic possibilities for change. This review outlines the major findings from a systematic search of the academic literature that identify the theoretical frameworks that best explain women's economic agency and investment decisions in agricultural contexts. Feminist theory, intrahousehold bargaining models, and asset-based frameworks (in popular use) are organized together because they are more complementary than contradictory, together providing an integrated view of why gender disparity in agricultural investment exists. They are also particularly valuable for informing successful change strategies that will empower women as participants in agriculture and enable them to have decision-making authority over their on-farm economic activity. Women's authority in agriculture is a social justice issue and more importantly they will be able to contribute to economic productivity and other development goals.

Feminist theories provide the broadest perspective for understanding the structural and normative constraints on women's agency, shifting away from individual choice, and examining how power relations, social norms, and institutional biases systematically constrain economic opportunity. The work of Spangler and Christie (2020) in Nepal using Feminist Political Ecology (FPE) examined how gender mediates environmental knowledge and access to resources. Anderson et al. (2020) utilized a feminist economic empowerment frame to critique the assumptions evident in development programs in the sub-Saharan Africa and South Asia contexts, asserting that to maximize agency, it is not enough to have resources, but one must have the authority to make decisions about those resources. Furthermore, Jackson (2007) and Petesch et al. (2018), also in the contexts of sub-Saharan Africa, used both intersectional and local normative frameworks, noting that agency is shaped by local "normative climates" and other local institutions such as marriage and kinships. These normative climates can act as socially constitutive, or constraining, or both. **Intrahousehold bargaining models** are mainly concerned with the micro-dynamics that occur within households. Its model households as units of cooperation and conflict where resource allocation is determined by the relative power and bargaining position of members within a household. Interventions that raise the autonomous income of women—through income diversification, value-chain membership, or cooperatives—improve their bargaining power in the household (Agarwal, 1997; Quisumbing et al., 2014). Schultz (1999) and Sloomaker's (2013) research emphasize that a woman's

bargaining power is significantly shaped by her investments in human capital — education or health, and her earnings, which together enhance her ability to bargain for a larger share of the resources within a household. However, these bargaining and negotiation models are often criticized for treating households as a "black box," and usually downplay the strong influence of socially constructed and institutional barriers that pre-structure and regulate the bargaining role, which is an essential gap that structural analysis can broaden in feminist theories.

From the **capability approach**, change must enhance women's substantive freedoms. This does not only require resources but also the agency to utilize them (Sen, 1999). This approach is intrinsically linked to the physical and non-physical assets women have, from asset ownership as the base of the economic contract. Meinzen-Dick et al. (2011) articulate a distinction between access, control, and ownership of non-market and market assets in a way that lends itself to change through agricultural development programs aimed at addressing the gender asset gap. Anderson et al. (2020) support this perspective, as they argue the availability of the right input/asset enables women to strategically invest and increase their income and have choices and decisions they make regarding that investment income and income-generating potential. Providing women with control then creates a self-fulfilling feedback loop as she builds wealth in the household and community (Anderson et al., 2020; Meinzen-Dick et al., 2011)

These theoretical positionings are not mutually exclusive but are interconnected and provide a holistic understanding of women's involvement in Agricultural Investment. Feminist theories explain why through uncovering the patriarchal norms and institutional structures that cause and maintain disparities, while bargaining models explain how through outlining the micro-mechanisms of power and negotiations within households. At the same time, asset-based frameworks provide what—the tangible resources over which bargaining happens and what feminist frameworks aim to distribute equitably. Agency is therefore made possible through a variety of socio-economic and cultural factors (from feminist theory, bargaining models and asset-based frameworks).

Figure 1. Conceptual framework of the study, constructed by the Author based on the key existing studies.

3. Methodology

3.1 Description of the Study Area

The Southwest Ethiopia Regional State was split from the former southern nations, nationalities, and Peoples Region (SNNPR) and officially designated in 2021 as one of Ethiopia's eleven regional states. The region has a total area coverage of 3,906,040 square kilometers and consists of six Zonal administrations i.e Kaffa, Sheka, Bench Sheko, Dawro, West Omo and Konta special Woreda. The region has a total population size of 3,501,832 and urban and rural households are 129,508 and 654,452 respectively. The region is characterized by a range of agro-ecological zones representing transitional rainforests at an elevation of 450-650 meters typically semi-deciduous forests to evergreen montane forests which are found higher up. This combination of richness in ecological forms makes the region ideal for a wide range of agricultural productivities and growing conditions, including the production of export cash crops such as coffee and tea. The official working language of the region is Amharic.

3.2 Research Methods

In this study, a convergent mixed-methods design was used to integrate quantitative and qualitative approaches for a comprehensive examination of women investors' land use performance in Southwest Ethiopia. Quantitative components used structured surveys to measure land allocation, crop yields, and employment creation. Qualitative element and key informant interviews (KIIs), examined contextual challenges associated with governance issues, capacity challenges faced by investors, and environmental concerns. In using a convergent approach to integrate both data sets during analysis, we will have promoted triangulation, thus optimizing the validity and breadth of the study findings.

3.3 Sampling

Through a complete census of all 315 agricultural investors in Southwest Ethiopia - 258 (81.9%) male, 39 (12.4%) in joint management, and 18 (5.7%) female farmland enterprises - it was possible to conduct comprehensive gender-disaggregated analyses of land use performance and production constraints. This method made it possible to case study the ideal region in terms of ecological advantage and temporal stability of agricultural investment. In addition, qualitative data was also collected from 8 purposively sampled key informant interviews representing 6 zonal, 1 regional, and 1 federal, thus giving attention to gender representation in responses. This mixed method approach resulted in a more complete analysis of gender inequities across the full spectrum of agricultural investors in Ethiopia.

3.4 Methods Data Collection and Analysis

The study used structured investment survey tools and semi structural interview questions to collect primary data from the respondents. The quantitative survey was collected using Kobo Toolbox, to including as land allocation (hectares transferred, cultivated, and uncultivated), types of crops grown, irrigation use, capital used for investment, and employment data. Qualitative data were collected from six key informant, drawn from government officials and sector professionals with their expertise related to the agriculture sector. In addition, document analysis has been carried to collect idea generated from past document research. The collected quantitative data was analyzed using SPSS. Descriptive and inferential statistics were performed. Methods such as means, frequency and standard were used to describe the data. In addition, ANOVA and chi-square tests to explore gender differences production. land use and challenges faced. Qualitative data was used to support the finding generated from empirical results.

3.5 Ethical Considerations

The research adhered to strict ethical protocols that included written informed consent, anonymizing the responses of the participants, and storing data securely (e.g., anonymity). Additionally, to remain culturally sensitive, female enumerators were hired as facilitators for

the FGDs in the Amharic language (the working language of the region). The facilitators informed the participants about the aims of the research and the participant's right to withdraw from participation, which proved helpful in developing a relationship of trust which was meant to mitigate any bias in their responses.

4. Results and Discussions

4.1. Pattern of Agricultural Investment in by gender

The descriptive statistics, Table 1, shows significant variations in capital and land ownership by sex (Male, Female, and Both). Male makes up the largest category (N = 253) for capital and has the highest mean capital (22.5 million) and median (14.5 million) but is skewed to the right due to some high values (max = 236 million). Female form a much smaller category (N = 18) than male with lower mean (15.8 million) and median (10.7 million). This suggests a systematic decrease in capital ownership compared to Male. Mean capital for agricultural investment owned by both gender (N = 39) is 76.2 million which indicates that ownership is important, but the value also has substantial variation (SD = 218 million) and few very large holdings (max = 1.19 billion); however, the median capital was 20.6 million, which is closer to male's median capital and reflects the variability as seen in the skewness.

A comparable pattern persists in land ownership where men dominate in both Agricultural investment (N=258) and average holdings (mean = 293 hectares, median = 200), and hold considerable variability over land ownership (SD = 519). On the other hands, Females investors shows to have lower averages (mean = 134, median = 128) along with lesser variability (SD = 116), indicating that females own less land, but consistently. The Both sex categories exhibits the highest mean landholding (553 per hectares) but also the highest variability in ownership (SD = 1,558), with a median of 210 closer to males as compared to females. This indicates that joint business ownership covers the range of both smaller and exceptionally large landholdings (max = 9,948). The findings highlight gendered inequalities in resource ownership - men are consistently hold more capital and land than females. The "Both" sex categories had a high mean and also positive skew in distribution (Large mean with positive skew could indicate that while joint ownership such as family holdings, partnerships etc. aggregating resources, they do not constitute the rule for most individuals).

Table 1. Descriptive statistics on the pattern of Agricultural Investment

Variable	Sex	N	Mean	Median	SD	Min	Max
Capital (Birr)	Male	253	22.5	14.5	28.4	0.1	236
	Female	18	15.8	10.7	15.5	0.15	45
	Both	39	76.2	20.6	218	1	1,190
Land leased (Per hectares)	Male	258	293	200	519	0.01	4,236
	Female	18	134	128	116	10	500
	Both	39	553	210	1,558	10	9,948

Source: Author Own Computation Using SPSS

The data shows that there is considerable variation in cultivation patterns relating to land ownership between male, female, and jointly-owned (Both). M males predominated in member sample numbers and land size, with cultivated area of 197.8 (median=72.3) and F females had 54.4 (median=21.6). Both ownership status had the largest mean (322.2) but also larger standard deviation (SD=990.2), indicating a range from smaller joint plot to much larger! This example is also seen for rainfed cultivation as the primary form of agriculture, where M males cultivated on average over 4 times the amount of land than F females. A similar pattern emerges for uncultivated land, but in this case female-owned plots (mean=80.0) were greater than their

cultivated plots (mean=54.4), which might indicate underutilization of land or possibly differences in land use.

Noteworthy, irrigated farming is low across groups (medians=0), but females and joint owners had higher means (5.9 and 11.9 units, respectively) than males (1.7). This could point to gendered access to irrigation infrastructure or differences in farming methods. Regardless, the Shapiro-Wilk tests (all $p < 0.001$, $W \leq 0.767$) demonstrate that all data are severely non-normal, with heavily right-skewed distributions due to most farmers being smallholders and outliers being large (e.g., "Both" max=6,281 cultivated units).

Table 2. Pattern of Agricultural land Use Practices by Gender

									Shapiro-Wilk	
	Sex	N	Mean	Median	Sum	SD	Minimum	Maximum	W	p
Cultivated	Male	258	197.79	72.3	51030	487.06	0	4236	0.376	0.001
	Female	18	54.42	21.6	980	73.17	0	270	0.767	0.001
	Both	39	322.19	115	12566	990.16	0	6281	0.259	0.001
Uncultivated	Male	258	94.98	36.6	24505	151.88	0	1057.2	0.641	0.001
	Female	18	80	31.5	1440	92.6	0	230	0.74	0.001
	Both	39	231.23	110	9018	580.52	0	3667.3	0.324	0.001
Raincult	M	258	196.06	70.7	50585	487.05	0	4236	0.374	0.001
	F	18	48.54	12.8	874	74.78	0	270	0.702	0.001
	Both	39	310.35	115	12104	958.72	0	6075	0.262	0.001
Irrigcult	M	257	1.73	0	445	9.5	0	100	0.183	0.001
	F	18	5.89	0	106	15.38	0	50	0.436	0.001
	Both	39	11.85	0	462	39.18	0	206	0.348	0.001

Source: Author Own Computation Using SPSS

Table 3 shows the patterns of land use productivity differences across male, female, and joint ownership groups. The Kruskal-Wallis test was used to analyze differences between three groups. The findings of the Kruskal-Wallis test provide strong evidence of significant gender-based differences in the productivity of land for agriculture across land use types (all p values < 0.05). The gender differences in rain-fed cultivation systems were found to be the most severe ($\chi^2=.12$, $p=.002$) suggesting that the problem for women related to agricultural productivity on rain-fed systems may lie with the fact they may not have the same access to climate adaptive behaviors, technology or decision-making on land use compared to male farmers. Significant gaps in both uncultivated ($\chi^2=11.60$, $p=.003$) and cultivated ($\chi^2=11.11$, $p=.004$) lands indicates a systematic gender inequality in land use practice and productivity. Irrigation systems showed smaller differences ($\chi^2=6.29$, $p=.043$) and while still significant, the smaller coefficient indicate a better outcome for gender access to irrigation systems of crop production. Even with irrigation systems being planned future research should continue to investigate gender identified differences in productivity although the significance may be diluted in a more controlled farming environment. Overall, these set of findings provide strong evidence for the noted hypothesis that productivity of land use differed by gender and that gender significant differences were greatest in the most climate vulnerable (rain-fed) systems. The results indicate the requirement for gender agricultural policy to identify the specific constraints facing women as they differ across the types of land use productivity systems.

Table 3. One-Way ANOVA (Kruskal-Wallis Non-parametric)

Land Use status	χ^2	Df	p
Cultivated	11.11	2	0.004
Uncultivated	11.6	2	0.003
Rain cultivation	12.18	2	0.002
Irrigation cultivation	6.29	2	0.043

Source: Author Own Computation Using SPSS

Post-hoc analyses, using Dwass-Steel-Critchlow-Fligner test, provided significant differences between the groups (Table 3) in terms of Cultivated and un Cultivated land. Jointly owned plots produced significantly more cultivated land than female owned plots ($p = 0.003$), as well as more rainfed cultivated land ($p = 0.002$), suggesting that joint ownership provides larger agricultural benefits compared to female farmers. Male farmers cultivated notably more rainfed land compared to female farmers ($p = 0.023$), highlighting the gender implications regarding land access and productivity. In summary, these comparisons demonstrate that female farmers face systematic barriers to cultivating land compared to joint or male farmers, which may limit opportunities and food security. Table land use choice for major crop

Post-hoc analyses using Dwass-Steel-Critchlow-Fligner test provided significant differences between the groups (Table 4 and Table 5) in terms of Cultivated and un Cultivated land. The only significant difference found by the Dwass-Steel-Critchlow-Fligner post-hoc test for cultivated land was female vs Both ($W=4.62$, $p=0.003$). The comparisons between M v F ($W=-3.15$, $p=0.067$) and M v Both ($W=3.19$, $p=0.062$) were not significant. This indicates that in cultivated conditions, the combined group (Both) was significantly different than the female, but males and females were not significantly different from each other or from the combined group (Both). Concerning uncultivated land, the DSCF test showed one significant difference between Male vs Both ($W=4.782$, $p=0.002$). Other comparisons, Male vs Female ($W=0.553$, $p=0.919$), and Female vs Both ($W=2.728$, $p=0.131$), were not significant. This indicates that in uncultivated conditions, the males differed significantly from the combined group, whereas the females did not find significant differences from males or from the combined group.

Table 4. Pairwise comparisons of cultivated between all genders.

Sex		W	p
Male	Female	-3.15	0.067
Male	Both	3.19	0.062
Female	Both	4.62	0.003

Source: Author Own Computation Using SPSS

Interestingly, Table 5 shows there was a prominent finding from the metrics of analysis of uncultivated land. Jointly owned plots were made of significantly more uncultivated land compared to male-owned plots ($p = 0.002$), but their size was larger overall. This could mean that joint ownership of land creates some intensity of land use that could be explained by difficulties of collective decision-making, divided land-use strategies or that it is over inheritance patterns where jointly held land is left uncultivated for future generations. In contrast, male-owned plots were more consistent in cultivation and present two perhaps distinct managements by joint-ownership and individual ownership.

Table 5. Pairwise comparisons – uncultivated between Gender

Pairwise		W	p
Male	Female	0.553	0.919
Male	Both	4.782	0.002
Female	Both	2.728	0.131

Source: Author Own Computation Using SPSS

The post-hoc pairwise comparisons for rainfed cultivation (raincult), Table 6, indicates significant differences between male (M) and female (F) cultivators ($W = -3.73$, $p = 0.023$) and female and mixed-gender (Both) groups ($W = 4.77$, $p = 0.002$), while male and joint ownership, while approaching significance ($W = 2.91$, $p = 0.099$). Overall, females were significantly different compared to both males and jointly owned investment while males were slightly different compared to mixed-gender groups; larger sample sizes may reveal significance in a follow-up study.

Table 6. Pairwise comparisons of rain cultivated between gender

Pairwise		W	p
Male	Female	-3.73	0.023
Male	Both	2.91	0.099
Female	Both	4.77	0.002

Source: Author Own Computation Using SPSS

Table 7 presents Irrigation practices did not indicate statistically significant differences among groups (all p -values > 0.05), but there was a marginal trend for joint owners to irrigate slightly more than male farmers ($p = 0.086$). The overall low use of irrigation among all ownership types indicates larger systemic limitations, such as lack of water infrastructure or lack of financial resources. The small difference for joint owners may be due to collaboration capacity from bargain joint ownership, but the overall statistically non-significant results indicate there are no differences in the benefit of irrigation for any farmers, and improvements are needed in irrigation policy for farmers, regardless of ownership structure.

Table 7. Pairwise comparisons of Irrigation cultivation between gender

Pairwise		W	p
Male	Female	2.4556	0.192
Male	Both	2.997	0.086
Female	Both	-0.0956	0.997

Source: Author Own Computation Using SPSS

4.2. Women Access to Agricultural resources and farm Mechanization

Table 8 reveals significant gender disparity in resources available to agricultural investors in Southwest Ethiopia, with inequities resulting in systematic exclusion of females from critical components of agricultural support. Most concerning is the exclusion of female's investors from loan facilities (0% female vs 12.8% male), tax privileges (0% female vs 19% male), both which are necessary for business startup and operation. In addition, female investors had limited access to machinery (only 16.7% female vs 33.3% male), and company facilities (access rates of 66.7% for female stories and 82.9% for male stories). The total absence of any financial support for independent female investors suggests potential institutional bias in lending and tax exemption access which systematically harms female investors.

Notably, jointly investment by both genders had better outcomes than male only or female only investors on all dimensions measure, particularly regarding tax privileges (33.3% access) and

machinery availability (46.2%). This is indicative of the possibility that gender-inclusive partnerships can potentially alleviate some barriers women investors face. The pattern of disadvantage across financial, technological and infrastructural dimensions demonstrates how intersecting barriers restrict women's agricultural productivity. These reports demonstrate the need for targeted interventions designed to address just women's agricultural investment capacity, including gender-sensitive loan programs, equitable tax policy, and machinery and operational equipment access programs to expand women's documented capacity to invest in agricultural activities.

Table 8. Gender Disparity in access to Agricultural resources access

		Male		Female		Both	
		Freq.	%	Freq.	%	Freq.	%
loan Facility	no	225	87.2%	18	100.0%	34	87.2%
	Yes	33	12.8%	0	0.0%	5	12.8%
	Total	258	100.0%	18	100.0%	39	100.0%
Tax Privileged	No	209	81.0%	18	100.0%	26	66.7%
	Yes	49	19.0%	0	0.0%	13	33.3%
	Total	258	100.0%	18	100.0%	39	100.0%
machinery	No	172	66.7%	15	83.3%	21	53.8%
	Yes	86	33.3%	3	16.7%	18	46.2%
	Total	258	100.0%	18	100.0%	39	100.0%
Company facility	No	44	17.1%	6	33.3%	5	12.8%
	Yes	214	82.9%	12	66.7%	34	87.2%
	Total	258	100.0%	18	100.0%	39	100.0%

Source: Author Own Computation Using SPSS

Table 9 reports the descriptive statistics show major differences in agricultural equipment ownership by gender. Male respondents felt they owned more across all four categories than females. The average males owned more tractors (0.69 working and 0.19 in which females did not own any), tillage equipment (0.33 and 0.12, respectively), and chemical sprayers (1.64 and 1.18, respectively). The largest gaps were for trucks (0.44 and 0.12) and combine harvesters (0.05 in women owned zero equipment). Importantly, no female respondents identified owning a combine harvester; in our study at least, the gender divide over the high value equipment was stark.

When we considered joint ownership (Our "Both" measure), the average for some equipment increased dramatically (chemical sprayer to 2.74), suggesting a pattern of "shared use" may be the case for numbers owned; thus, sole female ownership may be less common. However, the standard deviations (particular for chemical sprayers with SD = 9.18 for "Both") indicates wide covariance as well, which interpreted as not only households owning shared or rented or jointly-owned equipment but also households which own many pieces of equipment compared to the majority of who own few or any.

The findings from this part of our analysis suggest structural barriers continue to limit women's independent ability to obtain agricultural machinery, which for many, is likely to limit their productivity and, thus, their decision-making with respect to the farming enterprise. Structural decision-making challenges, policy choices which promote gender sensitive financing, gender inclusive training, and cooperative ownership practices, would help close these gaps by redistributing access to high-value machinery accordingly.

Table 9. Women Access to farm Mechanization

Agricultural mechanization	Sex	Mean	Sum	SD
Number of tractor work	Male	0.6917	175	2.389
	Female	0.1875	3	0.403
	Both	1.0513	41	2.523
Number of tractors not work	Male	0.2032	51	0.659
	Female	0.0588	1	0.243
	Both	0.4872	19	1.862
Number of tillages	Male	0.3346	85	0.979
	Female	0.1176	2	0.485
	Both	0.8158	31	2.629
Number of combine harvester	Male	0.0474	12	0.517
	Female	0	0	0
	Both	0.1282	5	0.522
Number of planters	Male	0.0745	19	0.341
	Female	0.0588	1	0.243
	Both	0.1282	5	0.469
Number of chemical sprayers	Male	1.6429	414	5.634
	Female	1.1765	20	4.851
	Both	2.7436	107	9.179
Number of trucks	Male	0.4418	110	1.102
	Female	0.1176	2	0.485
	Both	0.9167	33	3.074

Source: Author Own Computation Using SPSS

4.3 Agricultural Investment Land use choice in South West Ethiopia

Table 10 reveals significant gender-based variations in agricultural production patterns, with coffee cultivation dominating across all groups (57.4% of male farmers, 38.9% of female farmers, and 43.6% of group operations). Male farmers show particular specialization in coffee and mixed cropping systems (78 cases), while female farmers demonstrate more diversified production with notably higher relative engagement in fruit cultivation (16.7% vs 2.3% for males). The Pearson Chi-Square test ($\chi^2 = 23.131$, $p = 0.010$) confirms statistically significant associations between gender and crop specialization, though caution is warranted as 44.4% of cells have expected counts below 5. These findings suggest that agricultural development programs should adopt gender-sensitive approaches, recognizing male dominance in coffee production while supporting female farmers' more diversified operations, particularly in fruit cultivation. The results highlight the need for tailored extension services and input provision that account for these gender-based production patterns, with special attention to addressing potential barriers to female participation in high-value crops.

Table 10. Association between Investor Gender and cropping system

Crop category	Sex			Total	Chi-Square Tests		
	M	F	Both		Value	df	P-value
Pulse	2.3%	5.6%	5.1%	2.9%	23.131	10	0.010
Mixed	30.2%	33.3%	48.7%	32.7%			
Livestock	3.5%	5.6%	2.6%	3.5%			
Fruit	2.3%	16.7%		2.9%			

Coffee	57.4%	38.9%	43.6%	54.6%			
Cereal	4.3%			3.5%			
Total	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%			

Source: Author Own Computation Using SPSS

4.4. Challenges for Women Investors in the Southwest Region

This report undertakes a formal analysis of the gendered constraints to investment, discussed from the perspective of government-side bottlenecks, investor-side problems, and natural disasters. The analysis reveals important differences in perceived issues between genders. The implications of these results for development policy makers and the practitioners who wish to address gender access to finance are substantial.

Government-Side Bottlenecks: The Systemic Barriers to Investment

The most common barrier is perceived lack of infrastructure with 23.0% male, 29.6% female and 13.9% group investors identifying it. Infrastructure is a challenge. Improvements in roads, telecommunication, electricity availability and irrigation capacity (or systems) are critically needed. Female investors showed more immediate concern with the lack of policies (3.7% as opposed to 0.9% of males) and with lack of research (13.0% as opposed to 7.9% of males), representing a knowledge and support gap specific for women investors only. Group investors were aware of incidences which were systematic problems of access insurance (7.2%) and "roadblocks" (5.2%) implying systematic barriers for institutional or collaborative ventures. There is a definite need for infrastructure development projects, which should be geared towards addressing gender issues, as well as gender-sensitive reform to the policy framework and streamlined administrative processes.

Table 11. Government-Side Bottlenecks

Bottleneck	Male (M)	Female (F)	Both	Total
Poor infrastructure (roads, electricity)	23.00%	29.60%	13.90%	241
Weak input/tech access	9.00%	7.40%	8.80%	99
Credit limited to irrigated agriculture	8.20%	3.70%	8.80%	90
Security problems	7.40%	3.70%	7.70%	81
Poor research support	7.90%	13.00%	7.20%	89
Lack of digitalized services	7.20%	7.40%	1.50%	69
Weak sector support (budget, staff)	5.90%	7.40%	7.70%	70
Bureaucracy for loans	4.20%	1.90%	3.60%	44
Checkpoints across regions	0.50%	1.90%	5.20%	15
Other issues	0.80%	0.00%	1.50%	10

Source: Author Own Computation Using SPSS

Investor-Side Challenges: Capacity and Compliance Issues

Capacity issues were the primary investor-side challenges (31.5% male; 29.4% female). The data provides troubling gender discrepancies with respect to specific operational issues: female investors reported more farmland conflicts (5.9% vs. 3.2%) and issues with their business plans (11.8% vs. 3.9%) and group investors in particular, with issues related to corporate social responsibility compliance (3.5%) and privilege management (4.7%). The non-compliance with Environmental Impact Assessments (EIA) impact on 29.6% of male managed operations suggests widespread regulatory challenges. Yan K. (2022) advocates for evident, need-specific

capacity building programs and regulatory guidance and enhanced, gender-specific business support services to foster investment success.

Table 12 Investor-Side Challenges: Capacity and Compliance Issues

Problem	Male (M)	Female (F)	Both	Total
Capacity problems (skills, finance, etc.)	32.20%	29.40%	22.90%	157
Farmland conflicts	3.30%	5.90%	7.20%	21
Corrupted mindset	0.80%	0.00%	0.00%	3
Weak corporate responsibility	1.50%	0.00%	3.60%	9
Misuse of privileges	3.50%	5.90%	4.80%	20
Lack of market access	3.30%	5.90%	2.40%	17
Land use transfer issues	0.50%	2.90%	0.00%	3
Lack of EIA report	30.20%	20.60%	22.90%	146
Poor camp facilities	20.70%	17.60%	26.50%	110
No business plan	4.00%	11.80%	9.60%	28

Source: Author Own Computation Using SPSS

Natural Calamities: Differential Risk Exposure

The gender-disaggregated analysis of environmental risks identified the following foreseeable exposures by sex: disease exposure was established as the significant risk affecting 80.5% of male-managed investments and 40.0% of female-managed investments, while female-managed investments were impacted relatively more by floods (40.0% versus 8.9% of males) and drought (20.0% versus 10.6% of males in intensity due to aquifer depletion). Female investors experienced higher relative risk to flooding and risk to drought than male investors, which suggests that effective adaptation strategies in the climate arena need to consider differential gendered exposure to risk, specifically relative to flood risk for female investors and disease for male investors. These differential effects show the need to create gender-inclusive climate adaptation strategies to implement within agricultural portfolios.

Table 13. Natural Calamities: Differential Risk Exposure

Calamity	Male (M)	Female (F)	Both	Total
Disease prevalence	80.50%	40.00%	68.80%	77.80%
Drought	10.60%	20.00%	18.80%	11.80%
Flood incidence	8.90%	40.00%	12.50%	10.40%

Source: Author Own Computation Using SPSS

4.5. Discussions

The notion of inclusive development is realized when women have a vital role in development actions. However, as this research has demonstrated and prior studies have stated, there is substantial gender inequality in Ethiopian agriculture that relates to inequitable control over productive resources. This research evidenced differences in resource access in crop-production resources such as capital (female investors had an average of about 15.8 million Birr and male investors averaged 22.5 million Birr) and land (female investors averaged 134 hectares, while male investors averaged 293 hectares). This supports asset-based theoretical perspectives which focused on control over "har resources being a prerequisite for economic agency and investment capability. In addition to disparities in resource access, there are differences in financial freedom where female investors reported 0% access to tax privileges and loan institutions whereas male investors reported access rates of 12.8% and 19%, respectively. This confirms with Abdisa et al. (2024) which argued that that female-headed households were 3.7% less productive due to lack of resource and Bedi et al. (2023) argument that lack of access to credit and poor production technology was limiting women's agricultural

investment. This finding is also consistent with the feminist political economy perspective which contends that institutional barriers are systematically restricting women's economic participation.

Patterns of productivity shown to have complicated gendered dimensions, which challenge the conventional assumptions of agricultural development. Meta-analysis of Asefa and Muluken's (2024) stated that farms that are ≤ 0.5 hectares yield 21% more efficiency. However, women often cannot capitalize on the prospect due to layers of compounding constraints. This empirical research in Southwest Ethiopia demonstrated that male farmers cultivate four times more rainfed land than females; the total area cultivated (hectares) also has significant gender differences (rainfed systems: $\chi^2=12.18$, $p=0.002$). This supports Gebre et al.'s (2021) findings of 44.3% higher maize productivity in male headed households and show that while smallholder efficiency advantages do exist on paper, gendered constraints disallow women from benefitting from those advantages in practice. The paradox appears most pronounced in the joint ownership, which showed the highest mean productivity, but also the most extreme variances to demonstrate the continued layers of intra-household inequalities. This reflect the intrahousehold bargaining framework wherein power dynamics shape and mediate the flow of resources and power within households, even in terms of formal joint agreements.

Structural and policy barriers present women with multilayered challenges to agricultural investment. Female investors in this study were shown to face increased farmland conflict rates (5.9% versus 3.2% for male investors) indicative of increased challenges to land security and business planning. Female investors also faced disproportionate climate risk burdens, as 40% of women reported poor flood experiences compared to 8.9% of male investors which resulted in sequential types of impacts on how to preserve capital in their investment and invested in group-based investing. These grassroots challenges highlight inadequacies at the national policy level established in the literature, citing for example the findings of Tsige et al. (2020) on lack of agricultural gender-mainstreaming policies and the documentation by Atsbeha & Gebre (2021) that only 15% of women farmers were given climate adaptation training that was gender-specific. The consistent trend of gender-mainstreaming policies that were legislated presumably to do good, do not translate into meaningful actions to support any female agricultural investor, represent what could be termed "policy phantom" - frameworks written to promote gender but fail to translate into support for female agricultural investors. From an Institutional Theory perspective, this gap exemplifies the disjunction between Ethiopia's progressive formal land system, and the strong, patriarchal informal institutions that govern daily interactions and resource access in Ethiopia. Legally women are granted rights, while custom restricts their ability to access capital and land.

These challenges that are at the grassroots level, reflect some of the challenges regarding national policy identified in the literature. For example, Tsige et al. (2020) identified policy relating to agriculture and explained how it was inadequate in supporting gender mainstreaming. Atsbeha & Gebre (2021) discussed the low rates of climate adaptation training for female farmers and found that only 15% of women farmers had received this training. The lack of implementation around gender mainstreaming appears to be an unresolved issues around budgetary allocations to gender related development issues, weak enforcement of gender mainstreaming activities and a lack technical skill to implement gender mainstreaming in agricultural ministries. Also, both levels of data suggest a form of failed policy that theoretically has supported gender in terms of agriculture investing but in practice both situations are treated as what can be considered a "policy phantom" - these are policy frameworks that had good intentions of being gender inclusive in agricultural investing, but they never resulted in a support system for female agricultural investors in any form. Policy phantoms are a result of token gender mainstreaming, a lack of accountabilities, and an inability to respond to the power structures that advance gender inequalities.

5. Concussion and Recommendations

5.1. Conclusion

This empirical study confirms to the existing empirical studies that challenges of women's participation and productivity in agricultural in Ethiopia is deep-rooted and complex. Women face many barriers to accessing agricultural resources including farmland, capital and inputs, resulting in restricted farming potential. Men still possess a larger ownership of farmland overall (a total average of 293 hectares compared to 134 hectares men possess) and more overall capital (men control 22.5 million Birr compared to 15.8 million Birr for women). Ultimately, female farmers continue to do majority of the unpaid agricultural work without due compensation and decision-making power. Additionally, women's mistreatment and exclusion are staggering, as evidenced by their scant access to the financial services that support agricultural activities (0% access for loans and tax privileges compared to men).

5.2. Recommendations

This study highlights that dismantling systemic constraints requires a transformative response at multiple levels. The following framework contains actionable recommendations that are specifically relevant for the Southwest Ethiopia Regional State, that are aimed at addressing the fundamental causes, or systemic barriers that create inequitable gender differences in agricultural investment. These recommendations build upon the interconnected layers of institutional weakness, cultural norms, economic exclusion, and climate vulnerability that currently constrain women in their participation and productivity. This framework aims to simultaneously strengthen formal systems, shift cultural mindsets, build enabling economic environments, and enhance use adaptive capacity to provide a comprehensive pathway to equality in agricultural development. This framework calls coordinated action by government agencies, financial institutions, traditional leaders, and development partners to promote a more inclusive and resilient agricultural sector in the region.

Bolster Formal Institutions and Bridge the Implementation Gap. Effective institutional reforms are essential for gender-inclusive agricultural development. The recommendations are: a) Adopt mandatory joint land certification and titling and conduct awareness campaigns on women's land rights; b) Require gender audits for all agricultural programs, including for resource allocation, extension, and credit allocation decisions, to avoid entrenching gender biases in programming; c) Require laws for minimum quotas of 30-40% women on land administration committees, cooperatives, and in water user associations as a prerequisite for inclusive governance; d) Require leadership training programs for women elected to comply with the minimum participation quotas; and e) Together, provide a secure asset base, equitable access, and opportunity for full participation in governance structures. In stable regions, it will be important to close the gap between policy formulation and policy practice, to enable formal institutions to be proactive and effect women's agricultural empowerment, so that reforms translate into meaningful benefits for women farmers.

Disrupt Informal Biases Using Culturally-Engaged Solutions. Informal customs or institutions eliminate any chance of a formal gender policy succeeding. These informal customs demand culturally-informed solutions. Building structured relationships, with those who hold traditional community authority, including elders and the Kafos, allows leaders to become advocates of women's economic empowerment while explicitly showing how community prosperity is dependent on inclusive agricultural participation. Media campaigns targeting local radio, can showcase recent success stories of local women farmers, while simultaneously educating women about their legal rights with regard to property and resource distribution. Curricula developed in local agricultural schools or TVET centres, can teach future extension agents to use a gender-sensitive lens in their delivery of education. Together, these strategies unravel the deep-seated patriarchal norms and still respect local cultural projects. Further, the

strategies taken together - engaging leadership, organizing media strategies, and changing the curricula - create a coordinated social-contextual space where women's agricultural activities are recognized, valued, and normalized. Lastly, the strategies for transforming biases is complementary to a dual-strategy of utilizing leaders to change mindsets, alongside knowledge and information dissemination, thus minimizing the possibility all informal biases inhibiting women's full participation in agriculture development are eliminated - whilst considering structural change through formal institutions in a legitimate pathway towards gender equality and equity.

Create Gender-Sensitive Sustainable Economic Pathways. Economic empowerment is the best way to influence women's participation in agriculture through ownership structures such as movements and access to collateral. There is the potential of a form of collateral system around movable assets in the way that women can have ownership of credit based on machinery or livestock or forms of warehouse receipts (rather than land) this directly addresses the tenure constraints. There will also be opportunities for grants and local inputs directed at women through regional Bureau of Finance and Economic Development can offer women seed capital to become mechanically powered and subsidize inputs - all with the component of technical capacity to work with women to develop implementable business plans grants and access to subsidized inputs. Women-only and mixed men and women cooperatives are important to achieve ownership and/or leasing of expensive high-value agriculture machinery. Their pooling of the mechanics costs can broaden access to better agricultural technologies. Using as inclusive cooperatives, which were established with subsequent training in governance and financial management and management of machinery connectivity, agricultural output and profitability is expected to improve. Accessing financial support and technological support will position women with expanded production capacity, market competition into nearby local markets, and ultimately develop their agriculture business from a sustainable standpoint. Gender responsive economic pathways, legal changes, and social interventions, will strengthen momentum for women to identify and harness opportunities for investment and productivity that will generate income, and develop the right conditions for gender equitable agricultural development.

Promote gendered climate resilience. Vulnerability to climate shocks and stresses is unevenly experienced by women in agriculture, and interventions aimed at reducing climate vulnerability must explicitly consider this unevenness. For example, for women who farm, targeted interventions may equip them with the means to adapt, select, and use climate-resilient technologies such as with drought-tolerant seeds and small-scale irrigation, and appropriate climate-related information. Index-based crop insurance products targeted towards female farmers and women-headed households should maintain low-premium subsidies, and train women on how to file simple claims and complete literacy-friendly documentation when using the insurance when faced with risks such as floods or draughts. In addition, women should also be incorporated into disaster risk management and climate adaptation planning, along with related capacity-building, childcare provisions, and transport services. Therefore, by mainstreaming gender everything from planning interventions to deliver resources, insurance and localizing participatory when planning interventions for climate resilience the framework will create gains in women's adaptive capabilities. Integrated and cohesive interventions such as these that include capacity building and institutional support will create both conditions for temporary safety and secure longer-term resilience in the new environmental conditions confronting women farmers by cultivating capacities leading to socio-ecological sustainability at the local governance levels, while contributing to regional sustainable agricultural development.

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